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Education as an effective tool for women empowerment

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Abstract

In the worlds of Swami Vivekanand "Women must be directed to solve their own problems in their own ways. Our Indian women are as capable of doing as any thing in the world". But this capacity of human being for a better quality of life can only be developed & increased through education. Education is the only process which makes a person to develop himself as a woman or a man. It helps the person to grow in all dimensions. The final result of education is a cultured person. Now this cultured person has also to achieve the goals of progress & prosperity. So, here arises the need for competency based career development through which not only are they empowered but in turn, they can extend it through their work to the community and vulnerable groups, thus leading to social development and particularly to the development of women through self-awareness and acquiring skills. It is worthwhile to create the awakening among women so that they can come up by taking care of themselves. The status of women can be measured from the importance given to women's education.

Women should be given information on the suicidal policy of elimination of girl children through infanticide and how it should be avoided. How to achieve gender justice and gender equality should be taught. Awareness on social evils such as dowry menace, how to be self-reliant to face calamities if encountered in life, to accept responsibilities in life, never to feel inferior to others and to develop positive attitude to life should be created in their minds by giving examples and precept. The necessity to be economically independent is to be taught to the girl-children. The above aspects are to be taken care of both at home as well as at schools to empower the girl children as they are our future .

Introduction

The prosperity of a nation depends on the status and development of women. Women are potential source to development as pointed out by our first Prime Minister Shri Jawahar Lal Nehru who said that to awaken the people, it is the women who should be awakened. Once she is on the move, the family moves, the village moves and ultimately the nation moves. Thus, she is the main architect of change in the society.

Despite the fact a daughter is never regarded as a full member of her family and she is kept under much more discipline and restriction as compared to the son.

No society can progress if awareness and developmental urge are absent among the women. A women's status in the family is the indicator of her status in society. Therefore, a change in the attitude of family members is of great significance in improving the status of woman in the family. Since the unit of attitudinal change in any society is the family, our best effort has to be directed towards understanding their attitudes and aspiration towards the status of woman.

The status of women, in patriarchal culture, is the first major issue we need to consider as it is the root cause of several problems in the family and society. The early curricula for women's education, in fact, stemmed from the patriarchal culture where women's role has to excel in the home such as child care, cooking, clothing and household management. Extension beyond the family did not arise as women's role was confined within the four walls of the family. The status of women can be measured from the importance given to women's education.

In general, the solution to the social, economic and political problems of human society is to be sought through appropriate education. Education is not a static phenomenon. It is an organic entity which is dynamic, it changes and develops to meet the demand of the environment and needs of the society.

Women's Empowerment

For more than a decade, the term 'empowerment' has been widely used in relation to women. Today, one hears this term much more often than terms like 'Women welfare', 'upliftment', 'development', or 'awareness raising'. In many cases the word empowerment has simply been substituted to describe the same strategies and activities, which were earlier called, 'integrated rural development', 'women's development', 'community or women's participation' etc.

But is empowerment merely a synonym for these words? Or is it different? If it is, what is this difference and what changes does it demand in strategy? The most important feature of the term empowerment is 'power'. So obviously, empowerment is about power and about changing the balance of power. In every society, there are powerful and powerless groups. Power is exercised in social, economic and political relations between individuals and groups. Power itself can be simply defined as control over resources and control of ideology. Empowerment, therefore, is a process aimed at changing the nature and direction of systematic forces which marginalise women and other disadvantaged sections in a given context. Thus, empowerment is a process not a product. The outcome of empowerment would then be a redistribution of power, whether between nations, classes, castes, races, ethnic groups or genders.

So, let us be clear once and for all that women's empowerment, if it is a real success, does it mean the loss of men's traditional power and control over the women of their household, control of her body and her physical mobility, the right to abdicate from all responsibility for housework & care of the children, the right to spend family income on personal pleasures, the right to abandon her or take other wives, the right to take unilateral decisions which affect the whole family and the countless other ways in which poor men and indeed men of every class- have unjustly confined women.

The process of women's empowerment will also liberate men: they will be freed from the role of oppressor and exploiter and become better human beings. They will be relieved of gender stereotyping, just like women. They will be free to discover, develop and openly express the so called 'feminine' traits within them which have been suppressed or deserted. They will be empowered too, in totally new ways.

Power and rights to be demanded by the powerless and oppressed, for it is they who have something to gain. Just as Marx exhorted the workers of the word in the communist manifesto, we could say "women of the word unite - you have nothing to loose but your chains" However the process of demanding justice does not necessarily begin spontaneously or arise automatically from the very conditions of subjugation. We should not like women's empowerment to result in more taking over men's power within same exploitative and corrupt society women's empowerment should lead to the liberation of men from the false value systems and ideologies to oppression. It should lead to a situation where each one can become a whole being regardless of gender and cause for their fullest potential to construct a more humane society for all.

At the very outset, it is important to state that there is no one magic formula, correct recipe or fail-safe design of empowerment. The entire process is so tentative and experimental, so relatively crescent that we do not as yet have enough substantial evidence as to say this or that is the right way.

Indicators of women Empowerment :

Empowerment is an active process and not a commodity to be transacted. Power can not be given away as alms. Power has to be acquired. Once acquired, it needs to be exercised, sustained and preserved. Women have to empower themselves.

The empowerment mechanism is easily enumerated. We all agree that if a woman has all the following, she can reach towards empowerment :

1. Higher Education :

Men and women are of equal rank but they are not identical. They are peerless pair being supplementary to one another, each helps the other. In framing any scheme of women's education this cardinal truth must be constantly kept in mind. Man is supreme in the out-word activities of a married pair and therefore, it is in the fitness of things that he should have a greater knowledge thereof. On the other hand, home life is entirely the sphere of women and therefore, in domestic affairs in the upbringing and education of children, women ought to have more knowledge. Not that knowledge should be divided in to watertight compartments or that some branches of knowledge should be closed to anyone, but unless courses of instruction are based on a discriminating appreciation of these basic principles, the fullest life of a man and woman can not be developed.

2. Health Care :

Health can be seen as a complicated web of factors, all of which are interdependent, and no one factor can be understood in isolation. Through the process of empowerment, women can improve their health status. With less expenditure of energy and with available nutritious goods, they may be in a better position to maintain and improve their health. Women's education has been identified as the most important determinant of children's

health. An educated woman is also able to follow small family norm which in turn helps in national development.

3. Legal Education :

Women themselves need to develop a self identity so that they can lead a life of security and dignity. This can be achieved by making them aware of their legal rights, and potentials. Legal education should be considered more seriously than anything else, because in recent years crime against women has assumed giant proportions. Today's girls are going to be future women and they may have to face the world where the crime rate is increasing day by day. This would also help to create awareness, understanding and sensitivity among them. Awareness of legal rights among women and girls is almost nil, therefore they should be made aware and legal education be provided to them.

4. Higher age at Marriage :

When the age of marriage is raised, it opens up new choices like decision making power, maturity and so on. Several evidences suggest that women who start the child bearing at an early age are disadvantaged by educationally and economically for the rest of their lives.

5. Economic Development :

Majority of Indian Women are economically under another's bondage. It is this economic bondage that is the root cause of the troubles of the Indian women and for the removal of this our energies must be directed. The joint family system of Hindus, a relic of a feudal age, utterly out of keeping with modern conditions, must go and so also many other customs and traditions. But the ultimate solution lies only in a complete refashioning of our society.

6. Adjustments in the family :

The problems of accommodating married women with children in the developing structure of the labour market, in terms of part time work, flexibility over hours, work at home, relenting after a broken career, and the possibility of starting another career after the children have reached school age, or are in other ways less physically or emotionally dependent on her, as it impinges on her career.

Government may offer welfare schemes for women. They may float anti-poverty programmes. They may launch projects for their upliftment. They may enact legislation to safeguard women's right. The government policies can only facilitate the process, reduce the hurdles and create atmosphere conducive to transformation. But it is the women who have to empower themselves unless they themselves become conscious of their oppression, show initiative and seize the opportunities. "No body will give you your rights. You have to get them through struggle and fight.

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